

**A DATA MEANING APPROACH OF
“SPORTS ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION” AND
“SPORTS COMPETITION ANXIETY” OF
INTER UNIVERSITY SWIMMERS**

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study was to compare Sports Achievement Motivation and Sports Competition Anxiety Levels between male and female Inter University Swimmers in India and to find out relationship between Sports Achievement Motivation and Sports Competition Anxiety among male and female Inter University Swimmers in India. For the purpose of this study, 25 male swimmers and 25 female swimmers were randomly selected from Inter University Swimming Championship held at Bangalore, India on October, 2018. The subjects' age was ranged between 18-25 years. To measure Achievement Motivation, Sports Achievement Motivation Test (SAMT) developed by M.L. Kamlesh in 1990 and to measure Anxiety, Sports Competition Anxiety Test (SCAT) developed by Rainer Martens in 1977, were introduced respectively. For statistical analysis and interpretation of data Mann-Whitney Non Parametric 'U'-Test and Pearson Product Movement Correlation were conducted. The level of significance was taken 0.05. The study found no significant difference between Sports Achievement Motivation and Sports Competition Anxiety Levels between male and female Inter University Swimmers. The study also found no significant relationship between Sports Achievement Motivation and Sports Competition Anxiety among male inter university swimmers but the study detected a significant negative relationship between Sports Achievement Motivation and Sports Competition Anxiety among female Inter University Swimmers.

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1. Introduction

The word 'Motivation' derived from the Latin word '*Movex*' or the '*Matum*' which means move, motor and motion. It is a move towards set goal therefore; motivation is force which energizes the behavior of a learner. The definition of Sports Achievement Motivation can be considered when it involves 'competition with a standard of excellent'. Sports Achievement Motivation has been considered as an important psychological factor in behavioral psychology. Achievement motivation has been found to be rewarding in competitive sports. It is an innate force that employed an athlete in the tasks which are challenging and most difficult to attain. Sports and physical activities are generally achievement oriented. Personal success in team and individual events can be evaluated against specific standards. One of the reasons of the variability in athlete's behavior is sports achievement situation wherein athletes perceive situations in different ways, owing to different needs for Sports excellence (Sandhu, 1992) [1]. Anxiety is one of the important psychological factors for determining athlete's performance. The simple definition of anxiety is feeling of unease such as worry or fear that can be mild or severe. Getting an excellent Performance from any competition is a byproduct of biological, psychological, sociological and physical robust constitution of an individual. In games and sports, physiological factors are the base to achieve good performance of an individual but at the same time, psychological factors play the key role to determine the performance level of an individual. However, great important is assigned to psychological parameters in competitive sports (Schilling & Hayashi, 2001) [2]. Most of the experts in sports field advocated that performance of an individual or teams are affected not only by their physical and techno-tactical ability but also by their psychological constitution.

2. Methods

The study was conducted on 25 male Inter University Swimmers and 25 female Inter University Swimmers in India. The subjects' age was ranged between 18-25 years. To measure Achievement Motivation, Sports Achievement Motivation Test (SAMT) developed by M.L. Kamlesh in 1990 and to measure Anxiety, Sports Competition Anxiety Test (SCAT) developed by Rainer Martens in 1977, were introduced respectively. The score was analysed according to SAMT and SCAT score analysis norms. For statistical analysis and interpretation of data Mann-Whitney Non Parametric 'U'-Test was employed to find out the deference in Levels of Sports Achievement Motivation and Sports Competition Anxiety between male and female inter university swimmers. A Pearson Product Movement Correlation was conducted to find out the relationship between Sports Achievement Motivation and Sports Competition Anxiety

among male and female inter university swimmers. Descriptive statistics: mean and standard deviation were used to delineate the average and variability of Sports Achievement Motivation and Sports Competition Anxiety.

3. Results

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Selected Variables

Variables	N	Mean	SD
SAMT M+F	50	22.52	6.52
SCAT M+F	50	19.06	2.90
SAMT Male	25	23.60	6.90
SAMT Female	25	21.44	6.06
SCAT Male	25	19.52	2.66
SCAT Female	25	18.60	3.12

Note: N = Number of swimmers.

Table 1 shows the means and standard deviations of the selected variables. The mean along with SD of SAMT, SCAT, SAMT Male, SAMT Female, SCAT Male, SCAT Female are 22.52 ± 6.52 , 19.60 ± 2.90 , 23.60 ± 6.90 , 21.44 ± 6.06 , 19.52 ± 2.66 , 18.60 ± 3.12 respectively.

Table 2: Mean and SD of Sports Achievement Motivation Test and Result of Mann-Whitney U-Test between Male and Female Inter University Swimmers

Group	N	Mean	SD	SEM	U	P
Male	25	23.60	6.90	1.38	254.50	.25
Female	25	21.44	6.06	1.21		

*Significant level at 0.05.

Figure 1: Comparative analysis of SAMT mean between male and female inter university swimmers in India

Table 2 shows no significant difference in Sports Achievement Motivation Levels between male and female Inter University Swimmers. The mean and SD of sports achievement motivation in male and female Inter University Swimmers were 23.60 ± 6.90 and 21.44 ± 6.06 respectively. The calculated U-value was 254.50 and P-value was 0.25.

Hence, The $P > 0.05$ clearly indicate insignificant difference in Sports Achievement Motivation Levels between male and female Inter University Swimmers in India.

Table 3: Mean and SD of Sports Competition Anxiety Test and Result of Mann-Whitney U-Test between Male and Female Inter University Swimmers

Group	N	Mean	SD	SEM	U	P
Male	25	19.52	2.66	.53	295.00	.73
Female	25	18.60	3.12	.62		

*Significant level at 0.05.

Figure 2: Comparative analysis of SCAT mean between male and female inter university swimmers in India

Table 3 shows no significant difference in Sports Competition Anxiety Levels between male and female Inter University Swimmers. The mean and SD of sports competition anxiety in male and female were 19.52 ± 2.66 and 18.60 ± 3.12 respectively. The calculated U-value was 295.00 and P-value was 0.73. Hence, The $P > 0.05$ clearly indicate insignificant difference in Sports Achievement Motivation Levels between male and female Inter University Swimmers in India.

Table 4: Correlation between SAMT and SCAT in Male Inter University Swimmers

Name of the variables	N	r	p-value
SAMT	25	0.122	0.56
SCAT	25		

*Significance level at 0.05.

Table 4 shows Pearson Product Moment Correlation among the selected variables with P value and sample size. A positive correlation was found ($r = 0.12$) between Sports Achievement Motivation and Sports Competition Anxiety among male Inter University Swimmers. The P-value $0.56 > 0.05$ clearly indicate insignificant relationship between Sports Achievement Motivation and Sports Competition Anxiety among male Inter University Swimmers in India.

Table 5: Correlation between SAMT and SCAT in Female Inter University Swimmers

Name of the variables	N	r	p-value
SAMT	25	-412*	0.04
SCAT	25		

*Significance level at 0.05.

Table 5 shows Pearson Product Moment Correlation among the selected variables with P value and sample size. A significant negative correlation was found ($r = -412^*$) between Sports Achievement Motivation and Sports Competition Anxiety in female Inter University Swimmers. The P-value $0.04 < 0.05$ is clearly indicating a significant relationship between Sports Achievement Motivation and Sports Competition Anxiety among female Inter University Swimmers in India.

4. Discussion and Conclusions

Based on the result of this study on Inter University Swimmers in India, it can be concluded that:

- a) there was no significant difference in sports achievement motivation between male and female, but sports achievement motivation is higher in male than female Inter University Swimmers in India.
- b) there was no significant difference in sports competition anxiety between male and female, but sports competition anxiety is higher in male than female Inter University Swimmers in India.
- c) there was no significant relationship between sports achievement motivation and sports competition anxiety in male Inter University Swimmers in India.
- d) there was a negative significant relationship between sports achievement motivation and sports competition anxiety in female Inter University Swimmers in India which indicate two possibilities. Firstly, if level of anxiety is high in female Inter University Swimmers the level of achievement motivation became reduce and secondly if the level of achievement motivation is high in female Inter University Swimmers the level of anxiety became decrease.

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